

Influence Of Super Over Experience on Competitive Anxiety Among Young Cricketers

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of the present study was to examine the influence of Super Over experience on competitive anxiety among young cricketers. Competitive cricket frequently exposes players to high-pressure situations, with the Super Over representing one of the most intense and psychologically demanding scenarios. A quantitative pre–post research design was employed for the study. Thirty young cricketers aged 14–19 years, selected from school and cricket academy teams through purposive sampling, participated in the research. Competitive anxiety was assessed using the Sports Competition Anxiety Test (SCAT) before and immediately after a simulated Super Over exposure. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and paired sample t-test. The results revealed a statistically significant increase in anxiety levels following Super Over exposure ($t = 19.243, p < 0.05$), indicating that such high-pressure situations elevate competitive anxiety among young cricketers. The findings highlight the psychological demands of Super Over scenarios and emphasize the need for structured psychological training and pressure-based practice to help young players manage competitive anxiety effectively.

Keywords: *Super Over, Anxiety, Competitive anxiety, Psychological Stress, Young Cricketers.*

INTRODUCTION: Sports play an important role in the physical, mental, and social development of young individuals (Weinberg & Gould, 2019). In addition to improving physical fitness and technical proficiency, participation in sports contributes to the development of psychological strength, emotional regulation, and the ability to perform effectively under pressure (Anshel, 2000). Competitive sports such as cricket frequently expose players to challenging situations that test their mental toughness, concentration, and decision-making abilities (Haardy, Jones, & Gould, 1996). In contemporary limited-overs cricket, the Super Over has emerged as a decisive and highly pressurized situation used to determine the winner of a tied match (ICC,2023). A Super Over demands rapid decision-making, emotional control, and peak performance within a very short period of time (Weinberg & Gould, 2019). This intense competitive environment creates significant psychological

and physiological demands on players, making it one of the most stressful moments in the game (Martens et al., 1990).

Young cricketers often lack the experience required to cope effectively with such high-pressure situations (Hardy et al., 1996). The stress experienced during Super Over scenarios can negatively influence confidence, focus, heart rate, anxiety levels, and overall performance (Martens et al., 1990; Weinberg & Gould, 2019). Due to limited exposure to such critical match conditions, young players may struggle to regulate their emotions and manage competitive pressure (Anshel, 2000).

Understanding the impact of Super Over exposure on anxiety levels is essential for improving training methods and psychological preparation. By examining how repeated exposure influences physiological and psychological stress responses, coaches and trainers can develop effective strategies to help young cricketers perform better under pressure.

Therefore, the present study aims to examine the effect of Super Over exposure on the anxiety levels of young cricketers using a mixed-method research approach.

METHODOLOGY: The study used a quantitative pre-post design to examine the effect of Super Over exposure on anxiety in young cricketers. 30 players aged 14–19 years from school and academy teams were selected using purposive sampling. Anxiety level was measured using the Sports Competition Anxiety Test (SCAT) before (pre-test) and immediately after (post-test) a simulated Super Over. Informed consent was obtained, and confidentiality was ensured. Pre- and post-test scores were analyzed using paired t-test to determine the effect of Super Over exposure on anxiety levels.

RESULT & DISCUSSION: The data from 30 young cricketers were analyzed to examine the effect of Super Over exposure on psychological anxiety. Anxiety levels were measured using SCAT before (pre-test) and after (post-test) a simulated Super Over. Descriptive statistics including Mean, Standard Deviation and Range are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1: Table showing the Descriptive statistics of Super Over Exposure between Pre & Post test data

Anxiety	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Range
Pre-test	30	19.3333	3.80864	16
Post-test	30	23.3000	3.93175	15

Figure 1: Representing the mean scores of Anxiety level in Pre-test & Post-test

TABLE 1: Table showing the Paired Sample t-Test Comparing Pretest & Post-test Anxiety Scores

	Mean Difference	S.D	t	Sig (2-tailed)
Pre-test & Post-test	-3.966	1.129	-19.243	0.000

A paired sample t-test was employed to examine the difference in anxiety levels of young cricketers before and after Super Over exposure. The results indicated a mean difference of 3.966, showing a significant increase in anxiety levels following exposure. The obtained t-value ($t = 19.243$, $df = 29$) was statistically significant at the 0.05 level ($p = 0.00$). The data 95% confidence interval for the mean difference ranged from 4.388 to 3.545, confirming that the change in anxiety scores was not due to chance.

The observed increase in post-test anxiety can be attributed to the psychological demands of Super Over situations. According to Martens et al. (1990), competitive anxiety intensifies in situations involving high importance, uncertainty of outcome, and perceived pressure to perform, all of which are characteristic of Super Over scenarios. Young cricketers, due to limited exposure to high-pressure match situations, may experience heightened cognitive and somatic anxiety when placed in decisive moments. Furthermore, Spielberger theory suggests that situational stressors can elevate state anxiety levels, particularly when individuals perceive inadequate coping resources. The Super Over environment, with its time constraints and performance consequences, likely amplifies stress responses, leading to increased anxiety levels observed in the post-test.

CONCLUSION: The study concludes that Super Over exposure significantly increases anxiety levels in young cricketers, highlighting the strong psychological impact of high-pressure competitive situations.

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